

Bladder cancer presenting as a retroperitoneal urinoma of kidney

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ABSTRACT Urinoma in retroperitoneal space is a collection of extravasated urine leaked from the urinary system. Bladder cancer followed by a spontaneous urinoma formation is very rare. This report describes a retroperitoneal urinoma caused by infiltrative carcinoma of the bladder. The patient was a 79-year-old man whose chief complaints were right flank pain and nausea. Our case visualised the leaking point of urine at calyceal fornix very well in the imaging study.

KEYWORDS urinoma, urinary bladder neoplasms, flank pain

Introduction

Urinoma in retroperitoneal space is a collection of extravasated urine leaked from the urinary system. This is often found in a patient with a renal trauma and with an iatrogenic injury of the urinary system. A renal forniceal rupture causes a spontaneous urinoma after acute obstructive uropathy [1]. Ureteral stones could cause acute ureteral obstructions resulting in spontaneous urinomas. Unusual causes of spontaneous urinomas are posterior urethral valves in neonates and found in women during the post-partum period [2]. However, bladder cancer followed by a spontaneous urinoma formation is very rare. Here we report a case of retroperitoneal urinoma caused by infiltrative carcinoma of the bladder. To the best of our knowledge, our report is the fifth case of retroperitoneal urinoma related to invasive bladder cancer. Primarily, our case visualised the leaking point of urine at calyceal fornix very well in the imaging study.

Case Report

A 79-year-old man presented to our emergency room(ER) due to right flank pain and nausea for three days. His symptom had begun as a right abdominal discomfort a month ago. He had taken

alpha blockers due to the voiding difficulties for several years. He did not have any history of gross hematuria, nor ureteral stones, trauma, or previous surgery. His physical examination revealed tenderness in the right flank region. For an evaluation of the right flank pain, abdominal computed tomogram (CT) scan was taken. The scan showed right hydroureteronephrosis and 6.4 x 4.2 cm sized urinoma along the right psoas muscle. There was a leakage of urine from the right mid calyceal area (Figure 1). Pre-contrast CT scan didn't show any evidence of ureteral stones. To relieve the obstructive uropathy, he underwent right percutaneous nephrostomy followed by antegrade pyelogram (AGP). There was urine leakage from mid calyceal fornix making dependent urinoma along the right psoas muscle (Figure 2). After admission, to evaluate the cause of obstructive uropathy, we did cystoscopy under general anaesthesia and found partially papillary and nodular mass around the right ureteral orifice. There was no urine jet from the orifice. With the impression of invasive bladder tumour, we did a transurethral resection of bladder mass (TURB). The pathology report showed invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma which was high grade, positive detrusor muscle invasion and positive multiple lymphovascular invasions. On the following week, radical cystectomy with ileal conduit was done. The pathology of resected urinary bladder showed remaining urothelial carcinoma at the right lateral and posterior bladder wall (Figure 3A), which extended to perivesical fat (pT3b, Figure 3B) and the right ureteral orifice (Figure 3C). The prostatic urethra and the prostatic duct showed carcinoma in situ. He is doing well at 12 months postoperatively.

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Figure 1: Contrast-enhanced CT scan of the abdomen showing 6.4 x 4.2 cm sized urinoma (solid arrow) alongside right psoas muscle and contrast medium leaking from mid calyx of the right kidney (arrowhead)

Figure 2: AGP showing contrast medium leaking from right mid calyceal fornix (solid arrow) making dependent urinoma (arrowhead)

Figure 3: Pathologic figures of a resected urinary bladder. (A) Partially papillary tumour mass at the right lateral wall with ulcerating lesion (solid arrow) due to the previous TURB. (B) Microscopic peri-vesical tumour invasion (solid arrow) is present at cystectomy specimen (H&E, X40). (C) Partially obstructing right ureteral orifice (solid arrow) by a papillary tumour (H&E, X20)

Discussion

The factors responsible for urinoma formation are continued renal function, rupture of the urinary collecting system and distal urinary obstruction [3]. Most commonly, it is associated with obstructing ureteral calculi. The acute obstruction which leads to a sudden rise in intra-pelvic pressure causes extravasation of urine through calyceal fornix. This is considered a protective physiologic mechanism which may protect the kidney from high-pressure injury [4]. This is also shown in patients with posterior urethral valves [2]. Whereas, the mechanisms underlying urinary extravasation in malignancy may be different from those caused by urinary stones. The forniceal rupture following malignancy might be relatively rare due to the gradual increase in intrarenal pressure and hydro-nephrosis [4]. The actual mechanism of urinary extravasation in malignancy might be unclear because a limited number of cases have been reported. An extensive literature search revealed only four cases of urothelial malignancy presenting with urinoma formation. In 1976, Twersky et al. reported the first case of a patient with peri-pelvic extravasation of urine due to tumour obstruction of the ureter [5]. The second patient presented with abdominal mass as a urinoma due to a bladder tumour involving ureteric orifice [3]. The third patient had a massive urinoma with a point of urine leakage at renal pelvis due to advanced bladder tumour [6]. The fourth patient had a large sub-capsular urinoma due to a bladder tumour at the trigon [7]. Our case visualised the leaking point of urine at calyceal fornix very well in the imaging study. This might be the first case which shows a urine leak at calyceal fornix in a patient with urinoma due to a bladder tumour. This reminds us that when retroperitoneal extravasation of urine is noted in a patient without any history of ureteral stones, trauma, or previous surgery, further evaluation for the malignant disease might be needed.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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